

THE SPIRITUAL POTENTIAL OF MUSIC IN THE FORMATION OF A STUDENT'S
PERSONALITY – AS A MEANS OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article raises the importance of using the spiritual potential of music as a means of education in the formation of a student's personality as a key issue. A creative student is an artist. In his upbringing as a person, in the formation of a high respect for art, his daily practical classes, musical art, creativity are the main means of education. The article interprets music as a means of education in achieving the spiritual perfection of a student's personality - inner freedom, spiritual feelings serving the student's mental peace.

Keywords: student personality, youth education, means of education, spiritual potential, human values, national culture.

INTRODUCTION

In the current conditions of information flow and technological progress, the healthy need for the spiritual and moral development of the human personality, especially the younger generation, is growing. Sharp socio-political changes in the world, the transformation of spiritual values, and a culture based on consumerism are having a negative impact on the human psyche. Especially in the process of forming the personality of young people studying in higher educational institutions, the formation of spiritual stability and high creative potential is becoming an urgent issue.

From this point of view, the spiritual potential of music occupies a special place as an important pedagogical tool in educating the student's personality. Music not only evokes aesthetic pleasure, but also educates the human soul, forming moral sensitivity, spiritual alertness, and inner harmony in it. Art is an integral part of human activity, and the human personality is fully and vividly manifested through and with the participation of art. Art plays an important role in the aesthetic education of the current and future generations. Art helps to develop their feelings in the spirit of humanity and human cooperation, and develops their creative abilities. Taking care of the upbringing of aesthetic perception in today's youth, we must teach them to use the emotions that arise from interacting with art in their lives and activities. Therefore, it is considered an integral part of the network of aesthetic education[1]. The analysis of the educational potential of music, its impact on the psychological state of the individual and its role in combination with social values has always been an interesting source of research. The main goal of the study is to identify ways to ensure personal development and spiritual maturity through the art of music.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Continuous changes taking place in various spheres of human activity create a state of distrust, hesitation, and even depression in society. The words uttered by F. Tyutchev in the 19th century: "Today, it is not the body that is corrupted, but the soul" most accurately describe the state of modern society. Today, the decline in the level of moral culture is felt not only among young people, but also in all strata of society. There is a gradual spiritual decline among people, and society is becoming more and more accustomed to negative and immoral phenomena; this ultimately leads to spiritual poverty. Against the background of the sharp acceleration of technical, computer and mechanical

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progress, the “spirit of culture” is disappearing, it is losing its significance. At a young age, a person is most susceptible to external influences, he is attracted by unusual, sharp, contradictory and incomprehensible things. It should be taken into account that the age of 18-22 is the period of the most active formation of the system of moral orientations and moral qualities. At this age, motivation changes, character is formed and stabilized, especially social roles in adult life – civil, professional and labor, etc. – are fully mastered. Therefore, this period is singled out as a central stage in the formation of personality.

According to researchers of the psychology of adolescence, this is one of the most complex periods in a person's life. During this period, a person acquires the ability to perceive the environment through feelings, that is, to change his views on the way of life and the values that surround him. Spiritual music is not only the keeper of spiritual traditions, but also performs a personality-forming function. In his article about the positive impact of spiritual music, I. Voznesensky says: “... music, especially singing, is so in tune with our soul and so subordinate to it that it serves as the most subtle and touching means of expressing our feelings. Through music, the most sincere, noble, high and sacred feelings are revealed, for which there are no suitable words and expressions in human language [2]. Today, higher education institutions are not limited only to providing knowledge, but also take on the responsibility of preparing students socially, spiritually and morally, ensuring their formation as complete individuals. In this process, the effective use of the educational potential of music is of great importance. Music, as a type of art that directly affects the human mind and soul, enriches the inner world of a person. The educational process through music can be carried out in the following main directions:

Through musical works, young people get acquainted with national and world culture, which expands their cultural views and serves to form individuals ready for cultural dialogue.

Music involves students in social communication in the form of collective activities – choir, ensemble, orchestra. This forms social qualities such as cooperation, responsibility, mutual respect. As a psychotherapeutic tool, music helps to overcome problems such as stress, depression, and social pressure. The rhythm, tone, timbre and melody of music have a direct impact on the state of mind. Also, the educational impact of music is inextricably linked with the formation of personal motivation, the development of internal discipline, and the formation of a conscious attitude towards life. Musical and educational work with students gives significant results in increasing their activity in classes, raising their moral level. The research methods used in this article are analytical (analytical) methods, scientific literature, articles, and monographs on music education were studied. The theoretical views of domestic and foreign scientists on education through music were analyzed. The following serve as a basis for research in education and the implementation of new pedagogical technologies in life:

- attention to the results of pedagogical innovations, selection of the most effective ones, preparation of recommendations;
- each educator should be a seeker, a creator, and popularize his creative achievements;
- creating opportunities for young people to use the works of the great scientists of our homeland along with universal human values;
- completely abandoning uniformity and exposition in lessons and moving towards discussion, thinking, supporting the listener in becoming an independent thinker, etc.

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Therefore, if educational and methodological recommendations are developed that combine education, creativity, dedication, research, and entrepreneurship, we will have fulfilled our duty [3].

CONCLUSION

The above analysis and research show that the spiritual potential of music is of incomparable educational importance in the formation of a student's personality. Since the student period is considered a stage of social and psychological formation of a person, the influence of music in this process not only enriches the inner world, but also helps the person choose the right direction in the social environment. Music, with its emotional and touching nature, quickly reaches the human heart and causes more internal changes than other educational tools.

One of the main activities in the art of music is musical performance. Listening to an excellent performance, we experience feelings of pleasure, joy, inspiration, or, as the Greeks said, "catharsis" – a process of internal, spiritual purification and renewal. The performer is the link connecting the composer, the composer and the listener. The differences in the art of musical performance depend on the specific characteristics of the musical instrument, the form of solo and mass performance, the genre and formal nature of the musical work, and, first of all, on the creative individuality, the level of professional training and skill of the performer. For the performer, it is very important to understand and feel the psychology of the listener, correctly perceive the aesthetic requirements and mood of the audience, skillfully convey the author's idea, subjugate the audience to his will, awaken beautiful aesthetic feelings in the listener, and have a creative mood [4].

Thus, the educational potential of music, when effectively used in the modern pedagogical process, serves to educate the student's personality in all respects. This indicates the need to strengthen spiritual education in the higher education system, instill national values in the minds of young people, and recognize it as an important factor in developing a culture of intercultural dialogue.

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